

IT Students' Performance in Systems Analysis and Design with Educational Tour and Practicum Performance: A Correlational Study

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Abstract

This study determined the relationship of the IT students' academic performance in Systems Analysis and Design with Educational Tour (SADET) and practicum performance. This study utilized the final grade obtained by the students in SADET and the data from the evaluation form for practicum student. Statistical tools used were mean, standard deviation, and Pearson's correlation. The academic performance of IT students in SADET was "good", while their practicum performance was "excellent". A strong, direct, and significant relationship was found between IT students' academic performance in SADET and practicum performance.

Introduction

Bachelor of Science in Information Technology (BSIT) program was offered at John B. Lacson Foundation Maritime University-Molo, Inc. (JBLFMU-Molo) starting academic year 2003-2004 ("JBLFMU Molo", n.d.). It was renamed to Bachelor of Science in Maritime Information Technology (BSMIT) effective academic year 2005-2006. But, the program was renamed back to BSIT effective academic year 2011-2012.

BSIT is a 4-year degree program that focuses on the study of information technology and information resources needed to develop, manage, and maintain information technology infrastructure. It covers the learning of necessary knowledge and skills to effectively and efficiently utilize the benefits of information and communications technology. This program prepares students to be socially responsible and globally competitive IT professionals capable of developing systems for a more convenient and faster way of doing pertinent transactions ("Bachelor of Science in Information Technology", n.d.).

Among the courses offered under BSIT program are Systems Analysis and Design with Education Tour (SADET) and 486-hour Practicum (ITPract). SADET covers the learning of the different tools and techniques to system development. It includes educational tour not only for exposure to various IT industries and business processes, but also for understanding of the roles of IT in the different systems ("SADET", n.d.). It is offered during the first semester of third year. While, ITPract includes the exposure and supervised training of senior students to actual work ("ITPract", n.d.). This is offered during the first semester of fourth year.

The only correlational study on the academic performance of JBLFMU-Molo's IT students conducted was between College Algebra and Discrete Structures. The study (Aller, et al., 2011) revealed a positive and significant relationship in the academic performance of students between College Algebra and Discrete Structures. Hence, this study was conducted to augment such type of research output.

This study was conducted to determine the relationship in the academic performance of students in SADET and ITPract performance. The conceptual framework of this study is depicted in Figure 1. The independent variable is the IT students' academic performance in Systems Analysis and Design with Educational Tour, while the dependent variable is the IT students' practicum performance.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

Statement of the Problems

This study determined the relationship between IT students' academic performance in Systems Analysis and Design with Educational course and their practicum performance. Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions.

1. What is the academic performance of IT students in Systems Analysis and Design with Educational Tour?
2. What is the practicum performance of IT students?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the IT students' academic performance in Systems Analysis and Design with Educational Tour and their practicum performance?

In view of the abovementioned problems, the following null hypothesis was tested at the 0.05 level of significance: There is no significant relationship between the IT students' academic performance in Systems Analysis and Design with Educational Tour and their practicum performance.

Significance of the Study

The results of this study will benefit the students, teachers, curriculum designers, and researchers. The students may assess their academic standing in SADET and practicum performance. Furthermore, students will be informed of the relationship on the academic performance of students involved in this study. The teachers will be informed about the performances of their students in SADET and practicum. They will be informed of the relationship in students' performance in certain courses. The curriculum designers will be informed of the relationships of the courses included in this study and may consider the results

sin the enhancement of curriculum. Researchers may deem the results useful for further investigation.

Delimitation of the Study

This study covered only the batch of students who passed the SADET course last first semester, academic year 2014-2015 and completed their practicum requirements during first semester, academic year 2015-2016. Only 14 students were considered in this study.

The final grade of students in SADET was utilized as basis of their academic performance while the evaluation of their respective host establishment representatives was the basis of their practicum performance.

Methodology

This study utilized the descriptive research design. A descriptive study is one in which information is collected without changing the environment and is sometimes referred to as “observational” or “correlational” study (“Descriptive Studies”, n.d.).

The Sample

A sample of grades was taken from the BSIT students who passed the SADET course last first semester, academic year 2014-2015. The same students who enrolled in ITPract last first semester, academic year 2015-2016 and completed their requirements on or before December 31, 2015. Only fourteen (14) students had the complete data based on the grade sheets and evaluation of their respective host establishment representatives.

Only their final grade in SADET became the basis of their academic performance, while mean evaluation obtained from the evaluation sheet for practicum student was the basis of their practicum performance.

Table 1 shows the details of the courses used as sample.

Table 1
Details of the Courses for the Sample

Course	Academic Year	Semester
Systems Analysis and Design with Educational Tour	2014-2015	1 st
Practicum (486 hours)	2015-2016	1 st

Materials and Instrumentation

This study made use of the grade sheet for the SADET course during the first semester, academic year 2014-2015 to obtain the IT students’ academic performance. Only the final grade was used.

To describe the academic performance, the following scale patterned from the student manual was used:

Range	Description
93.50 - 100.00	Excellent
87.50 - 93.49	Very Good
84.50 - 87.49	Good
79.50 - 84.49	Satisfactory
74.50 - 79.49	Passed
Below 74.49	Failed

The practicum performance was based on the evaluation obtained from the evaluation sheet for practicum student. The evaluation sheet contains 12 items; each is rated by 1, 2, 3, 4, or 5 corresponding to poor, fair, good, very good, and excellent, respectively.

To describe the IT students' practicum performance, an arbitrary scale below was used.

Scale	Description
4.21 - 5.00	Excellent
3.41 - 4.20	Very Good
2.61 - 3.40	Good
1.81 - 2.60	Fair
1.00 - 1.80	Poor

Data Analysis Procedure

Collected data were subjected to certain statistical tools according to computational needs.

Mean was used to describe the IT students' academic performance in SADET and practicum performance.

Standard deviation was used to determine the variation in the IT students' academic performance in SADET and practicum performance.

Pearson's correlation was used to determine the relationship between IT students' academic performance in SADET and practicum performance.

Results and Discussion

Table 2 shows the IT students' academic performance in SADET and practicum performance.

IT students' academic performance in SADET was "good" ($M=85.57$, $SD=4.05$), while their practicum performance was "excellent" ($M=4.64$, $SD=0.27$).

The variation in their SADET academic performance was small, as well as the dispersion in their practicum performance.

Table 2
IT Students' Performance in SADET and Practicum

Course	Mean	Description	SD
Systems Analysis and Design with Educational Tour	85.57	Good	4.05
Practicum (486 hours)	4.64	Excellent	0.27

Table 4 shows the relationships between IT students' academic performance in SADET and their practicum performance. The relationship was found to be strong as to degree, direct as to direction, and significant ($r=0.679$, $p=0.008$).

Table 4
Relationship between SADET and Practicum Performance

	Tourism Industry Overview	
	r	p-value
Introduction to Tourism Theory	0.679	0.008*

* $p < 0.05$

Conclusions

IT Students' performance in Systems Analysis and Design with Educational Tour was much higher than passing. This implies that students met the intended learning outcomes from the said course. Moreover, it proves that the student learning activities and the teaching methods used by the instructor in facilitating learning were complementary.

The excellent evaluation obtained by IT students in their practicum confirms the learning obtained by them from various school experiences. This implies that they met the expectations of their respective host establishment on the following aspects: accuracy and quality in carrying out assigned task, promptness in finishing assigned work, initiative and resourcefulness, faithfulness in reporting to work, harmonious relationship with others, observance of proper office decorum and sense of personal decorum, application of theoretical knowledge, and proficiency in communication, computation, and use of computers and other office equipment.

A strong, direct, and significant relationship between IT students' academic performance in SADET and practicum performance shows that as the academic performance in SADET increases, their practicum performance also increases. The results may justify having a requirement of senior standing before taking the practicum; students must have completed at least 80% of their professional courses. Some qualities they showed during their practicum may have been acquired from SADET course.

Recommendations

Students need to understand the importance of pre-requisite in their courses. Their value and good performance in the pre-requisite ones will contribute to their good performance in practicum. It is recommended for the students who have not yet taken SADET course to perform better in their class in order to have a good chance of acceptable performance in their practicum.

Although students' performance was good, Instructors in SADET and other course are encouraged to try other learning activities to maximize the learning of students and get an excellent grade. They are hoped to provide variety of relevant student learning activities in order to improve the academic performance of students in the next semesters.

Curriculum designers may consider the results of this study in asserting whether they must modify the requirements in taking practicum or they will remain firm with the prescribed requirements at present.

Researchers are encouraged to conduct similar studies but cover grades of students in other academic years. Moreover, future researchers may explore the effects of other grade components to students' academic performance in practicum.

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